

ANALYSIS OF ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION RESULTS OF THE HIP JOINT IN NEWBORNS

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Abstract. *Early and timely diagnosis of hip joint pathology in children is of significant importance for neonatologists, pediatricians and orthopedists, as delayed treatment of these conditions often leads to disability. The objective of the study is to improve the early diagnosis of hip joint pathology in young children. There have been conducted ultrasound examinations of the hip joint in 116 newborns at TashPMI clinic and the neonatal surgery department of the Republican Perinatal Center. The study showed the effectiveness of non-invasive ultrasound in diagnosing hip joint dysplasia, congenital hip dislocation, and epiphyseal osteomyelitis. This approach significantly reduced the need for further radiological examinations and enabled timely therapeutic interventions.*

Keywords: *hip joint dysplasia, congenital hip dislocation, osteomyelitis of the femoral head, diagnosis, ultrasound examination.*

Relevance

It is known that hip joint pathologies are one of the pressing issues in orthopedics and pediatrics, especially hip joint dysplasia, congenital dislocation, and epiphyseal osteomyelitis in newborns. There is no doubt about the importance of early detection of dysplasia and congenital dislocation of the hip joint. However, accurate assessment of the joint components is considered crucial for neonatal surgeons, pediatricians, and orthopedists (Buriyev M., 2006; Abdullaev M., 2013; Ergashov B., 2019). At an early age, the hip joint in children is not fully developed, and the bony part is smaller. Primarily, the femoral head and the wall of the acetabulum are covered with hyaline cartilage, while only the bottom of the acetabulum has a small amount of fatty tissue. The formation of ossification centers in the joints of healthy children takes up to 6-8 months. Therefore, radiological examinations of hip joint pathologies in infants cannot provide precise and complete information.

At present time, modern ultrasound examination of the hip joint in infants and young children is considered the best non-invasive method for determining the structure, delayed formation, and pathology of all joint components. In this case, not only can the state of the joint elements be assessed, but also the condition of the blood circulation, which is important when choosing the treatment method and improving its outcomes. Thus, the main objective of this study is to improve the diagnosis of hip joint pathologies.

Materials and Methods

There have been conducted ultrasound examinations of the hip joint in 116 children at TashPMI clinic and the Republican Perinatal Center. During the examination, we primarily identified the sonographic types of joints according to the method of R. Graf (Table N. 1).

Currently, in infants and young children, the structure, delayed formation, and pathology of all joint components of the hip joint can be determined using modern ultrasound equipment with 2D and 3D echography. The examinations were conducted according to the accepted standard

of R. Graf (1984, 1997) using the "Interscan" - 250 machine (Germany) and mobile ultrasound devices "Sonoscape s8," with sector and convex multi-frequency probes ranging from 3.5/5/7.5 MHz.

Table №1

Distribution of children by diagnosis and gender

Diagnosis	Gender		abs.	%
	Girls	Boys		
Healthy child	42	30	72	62,0
Hip joint dysplasia	14	11	25	21.5
Hip subluxation	4	4	8	6.8
Hip dislocation	4	2	6	5.1
Epiphyseal osteomyelitis	2	3	5	4.3
Total	66	50	116	100

Results:

A total of 81 children were examined at the TashPMI clinic and 36 children at the neonatal surgery department of the Republican Perinatal Center. In 52 (60.4%) children, hip joint of types 1a and 1b were diagnosed. According to clinical examination and sonography, hip joints of types 1a and 1b are considered healthy. In these cases, the edges of the pelvis are clearly visible, the "arch" line of the bone forms nearly a right angle, and the pelvic bone encompasses the femoral head. The bone-to-bone ratio is 2/3.

Certainly, in 72 (62.0%) children, hip joint of types 1a and 1b were diagnosed. According to clinical examination and sonography, hip joints of types 1a and 1b are considered healthy. In these cases, the edges of the pelvis are clearly visible, the "arch" line of the bone forms nearly a right angle, and the pelvic bone encompasses the femoral head. The bone-to-bone ratio is 2/3. The angle "a" is equal to 60°, and angle "b" is less than 55° - this corresponds to type 1a. If angle "b" is greater than 55°, it corresponds to type 1b.

It is known that in 25 (21.5%) children, simple hip dysplasia, i.e., only low ossification of the femoral head, is considered a condition that does not affect the structure and formation of the joint. The angle "a" is equal to 60°, and the angle "b" is less than 55° - this corresponds to type 1a. If angle "b" is greater than 55°, it corresponds to type 1b.

Additionally, hip joint of type 2a was identified in 8 (6.8%) children, where joint dysplasia has a pronounced type, and the combined structures forming the joint are underdeveloped. The angle "a" is less than 59°, but more than 50°, and the angle "b" is greater than 60°.

Moreover, hip joint of type 2b was identified in 3 (3.4%) children, where hip joint dysplasia had a clear type. In these cases, the edges of the acetabular cup have a rounded "arch" bone line, and only the upper part of the cup covers the femoral head. The angle "a" is less than 59°, but more than 50°, and the angle "b" is greater than 60°, indicating a condition of subluxation.

Definitely, hip joint of type 2 was identified in 6 (5.1%) children, where joint dysplasia has a severe type, and the overall structures of the joint are underdeveloped. The "arch" line of the bone is smooth and flat, the femoral bone is widened, and the femoral bone does not cover the femoral head. The angle "a" is less than 49°, but more than 43°, and the angle "b" is greater than 65°.

In type 2 hip joint dysplasia, if left untreated, it can lead to a congenital hip dislocation, which is clinically assessed as a congenital hip dislocation.

In 5 (4.3%) newborns, inflammatory phenomena were detected in one or both hip joints, with effusion. After radiological examination and joint puncture, osteomyelitis was identified. Besides that, for assessing blood circulation in the hip joint, there was used the method of color energy Doppler ultrasound, which allows us to determine the condition and diameter (mm) of the blood vessel walls, as shown in Table N.2. To determine the blood circulation speed (cm/sec), we used the method of pulsed Dopplerometry (PD).

Table N. 2

Dopplerographic Indicators (on Day 30) M+m in Children with Hip Dysplasia

Hip Joint	Type of Dysplasia			
	Type 2b and Type 2c (n=9)			
	Indicators			
	Speed (cm/sec)	Diameter (mm)	Speed (cm/sec)	Diameter (mm)
Right	72±0,05	2,71±0,01	68,23±0,01	2,6±0,01
Left	71,1±0,03	2,96±0,02	66,15±0,09	2,8±0,01

Conclusion:

By summarizing it should be suggested that based on the research conducted, ultrasound examination of the hip joint in young children helps to detect joint pathologies at an early stage, avoiding unnecessary and non-invasive X-ray radiation during further orthopedic examinations. Doppler ultrasound examination of the hip joint provides accurate assessment of the blood circulation in the joint. Timely treatment of the disease, in general, helps to prevent the exacerbation of the process and avoid various complications.

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